

Reimagining Tourism Management Education: The Role of Ideology, Innovation, and the 'Three Creations' Framework

Chen Yu Han and Zhang Wei Lin

Xingzhi College of Xi'an University of Finance and Economics, Xi'an, 710038, Shaanxi, China

DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15482387>

Abstract: In the era of new liberal arts, higher education institutions face the vital task of nurturing students' innovation, entrepreneurial mindset, and creativity. This imperative extends to applied disciplines like tourism management, where educational reform is increasingly pressing. The goals of tourism management programs have evolved in response to the dynamic socioeconomic landscape and the evolving expectations of tourists. Nurturing comprehensive innovation, entrepreneurship, and creativity among tourism management students is paramount, and it demands the integration of "three creations" education with professional ideology within the new liberal arts framework.

This paper explores the implementation and evolution of "three creations" education in tourism management through innovative classroom methods, extensive literature analysis, and comprehensive questionnaire surveys. The study advocates a synergistic approach that combines "three creations" education with professional ideology and politics to guide the cultivation of students. The ultimate objective is to offer valuable insights for education and teaching reforms in tourism management programs, ensuring that students develop a sound life perspective and values while honing their professional skills.

The proposed synergistic nurturing model aims to contribute to the field of tourism management by fostering holistic education and addressing theoretical and practical challenges in cultural education.

Keywords: Tourism Management, Innovative Education, Entrepreneurial Spirit, Creativity, Synergistic Nurturing Model

1. Introduction

In the context of new liberal arts, cultivating students' innovative ability, entrepreneurial spirit and creativity has become an important task of higher education. As an applied discipline, the tourism management specialty faces more urgent demands for educational reform in the context of the new era. With the rapid development of social economy and the continuous improvement of people's experience of tourism, the cultivation goal of tourism management specialty has changed dramatically. How to cultivate tourism management students to develop their innovation, entrepreneurship and creativity in a comprehensive way through the synergistic cultivation of "three creations" education and professional ideology under the background of the new liberal arts has become an urgent problem to be solved.^[1]

Therefore, this paper tries to explore the existence and development of the "three creations" education in tourism management majors through classroom innovation, literature research and questionnaire survey, and seeks to combine the "three creations" education and professional ideology and politics and put forward a synergistic nurturing mode. The ultimate goal of this study is to provide useful reference and guidance for the education and teaching reform of tourism management majors. Through the implementation of the synergistic nurturing model of "three creations" education and professional ideology and politics, students will be able to form a correct outlook on life and values at the same time of cultivating professional skills. At the same time, it will also provide new ideas and assistance for the practice and development of "Three Creations" education. Through in-depth

research and exploration, we aim to contribute to the development and innovation of the tourism management profession, as well as to the theoretical and practical issues in the field of cultural education.^[2]

Under the background of new liberal arts, the synergistic cultivation of "three creations" education and professional ideology in tourism management majors has attracted wide attention. Based on the actual teaching survey of tourism management teachers and the study of related literature at home and abroad, this study strives to explore and solve this problem, and provide theoretical and practical guidance for the development and innovation of tourism management majors. Through the development of this study, we expect to provide useful reference and guidance for the cultivation of innovation ability, entrepreneurship and creativity of tourism management students, and make our own contribution to the educational and teaching reform of tourism management majors.

2. The current situation of the development of tourism management major under the background of new liberal arts

2.1 The construction of new liberal arts background and its influence

With the continuous progress and development of society, the field of culture and pedagogy has also been deeply influenced by the new liberal arts background. The new liberal arts background refers to a series of new features and trends in the development and change process of liberal arts education in the new century. The construction of new liberal arts background plays an important role in the development of education and teaching of tourism management majors.^[3]

First of all, the educational methods and concepts under the new liberal arts background have undergone significant changes. The traditional education model focuses on the inculcation of knowledge and the cultivation of skills, while in the new liberal arts background, education and teaching pay more attention to cultivating students' innovative thinking and entrepreneurial consciousness. In this context, cultivating students' independent thinking and problem-solving ability

has become the focus of tourism management professional education.^[4]

Secondly, the knowledge structure and disciplinary settings in the context of new liberal arts have also undergone significant adjustments. As an applied discipline, tourism management majors need to intermingle with other disciplines to form a comprehensive knowledge system. Under the background of new liberal arts, tourism management majors pay more attention to interdisciplinary integration, combine disciplinary research with practical application, and promote tourism management education to develop in breadth and depth.

Again, the social demand and industrial development in the context of new liberal arts also have a great impact on the education and teaching of tourism management majors. With the rapid development of tourism, the demand for tourism management professionals is increasing. Under the background of new liberal arts, the social demand for tourism management professionals is even higher, requiring them to have comprehensive qualities and abilities, including innovation and entrepreneurship, marketing ability, interpersonal skills and so on. Therefore, the education and teaching of tourism management majors need to adapt to the needs of talent cultivation in the context of new liberal arts, focusing on the cultivation of practical ability and the training of intercultural communication ability.^[5]

2.2 Status and Problems of Tourism Management Major

Tourism management major is a flourishing discipline under the background of new liberal arts, which is closely related to the rapid rise of tourism and people's continuous demand for tourism industry. However, with the continuous development of the tourism industry, the problems faced by the tourism management profession have gradually appeared. First of all, there is a certain lack in cultivating students' practical ability and innovative spirit in the tourism management major. Although the three creative education has been introduced in this specialty, most of the current teaching mode is still the traditional theoretical indoctrination, which lacks practical operation

and practice links. Students lack the opportunity of practical operation and cannot really exercise and improve their practical ability. At the same time, the cultivation of innovative spirit is also insufficient, and students lack effective guidance and cultivation in innovative thinking and entrepreneurial awareness. This makes students often unable to flexibly apply the knowledge they have learned in the actual work, and lack of innovative thinking and creativity.^[6]

Secondly, there is a certain disconnect between the curriculum of tourism management majors and the actual demand. With the rapid development of the tourism industry, tourism management majors need to pay attention to the latest developments and trends in the industry in order to better meet the market demand. However, most of the current curricula are still in the traditional category and cannot be updated and adapted to the requirements of the new situation in a timely manner. This leads to the fact that students are often unable to effectively apply what they have learned after graduation, and there is a certain disconnect with the actual needs of the industry.^[7]

In addition, there are also some problems in the professional ideology of tourism management majors. Professional Civics refers to the cultivation of students' professionalism while focusing on the cultivation of students' sense of social responsibility and correct outlook on life and values. However, in tourism management majors, professional ideology and politics education is often neglected or lacks effective guidance. Students only focus on professional knowledge and technology in their professional learning, and lack the awareness and cultivation of social responsibility and humanism. This not only affects the comprehensive quality and professional ethics of students, but also restricts the sustainable development of the tourism management profession.^[8]

To address the above problems, we propose a collaborative education model that combines the "Three Creations" education and professional ideology. Specifically, we need to add practical links and innovation and entrepreneurship programs in the curriculum of tourism management majors to enhance students' practical ability and innovative spirit. At the same time, we should strengthen the research and cognition of tourism under the new situation, and adjust the course content in time to make it match the actual demand of the industry. In addition, we should strengthen the professional ideological and political education for students, focusing on cultivating students' sense of social responsibility and correct outlook on life and values. Through this collaborative education model, tourism management students can comprehensively develop their practical ability, innovative thinking and entrepreneurial awareness, while forming a correct outlook on life and values.

2.3 Application and Effect of "Three Innovations" Education in Tourism Management Majors

Under the background of new liberal arts, as a discipline integrating humanities and social sciences, tourism management majors need to cultivate students' professionalism as well as pay attention to students' innovative thinking and practical ability. Therefore, it is of great significance to implement the "Three Innovations" education in tourism management majors. First of all, the empirical evidence of the application of "three creations" education in tourism management majors needs to clarify the educational objectives and cultivation mode. Through literature research, we can find that there are relatively few empirical studies on the application of "Three Creations" education in tourism management majors, so we need to explore how to apply "Three Creations" education in tourism management majors to promote the overall development of students from multiple perspectives.^[9]

Secondly, we can obtain relevant data through questionnaire survey for the empirical evidence of the application of "Three Creations" education in tourism management majors. Through the questionnaire survey, we can understand the degree of students' cognition of the "three creations" education and the specific application in tourism management majors. At the same time, we can also obtain relevant evaluations and suggestions through

interviews with teachers and industry experts, in order to have a more comprehensive understanding of the actual application of "Three Creations" education in tourism management majors. Further research found that there are some problems and challenges in the application of "Three Creations" education in tourism management majors. Firstly, the existing teaching resources and platforms are limited, which hinders the full development of "Three Creations" education. Secondly, students' awareness of innovation, entrepreneurship and creativity needs to be improved, and we need to strengthen the publicity and guidance on the significance and value of "three creations" education. In addition, we also need to pay attention to how to combine with professional ideology in tourism management majors, so as to cultivate students' correct outlook on life and values.^[10]

In view of the above problems, this project proposes a collaborative education model, which aims to promote the organic combination of "Three Creations" education and professional ideology and politics in tourism management majors. This model will improve the application effect of "Three Creations" education in tourism management majors by adjusting the curriculum and optimizing the teaching methods. Specifically, we can promote the overall development of students by integrating the "Three Creations" education into the professional curriculum, offering related innovation and practice courses, and organizing innovation and entrepreneurship project competitions.

In addition, we can strengthen cooperation with the industry to provide students with practical opportunities and platforms for innovation and entrepreneurship, and help them improve their innovation ability and entrepreneurial awareness through training and practical guidance. At the same time, combined with the characteristics and disciplinary connotation of tourism management majors, professional ideological education is carried out to guide students to form a correct outlook on life and values.

3. Synergistic parenting strategy of "Three Creations" education and professional ideology and politics

3.1 Integration Strategy of "Three Creations" Education and Professional Civic and Political Education in Tourism Management

As a kind of education mode to cultivate students' innovation, entrepreneurship and creativity, the application of "Three Creations" education has been expanding in tourism management majors. However, how to realize synergistic cultivation between "Three Creations" education and professional ideological education has not been fully studied and explored. First of all, the integration of "Three Creations" education and professional ideological education needs to have clear goals and concepts. In tourism management majors, this project believes that "three creations" education should be integrated with professional ideology, not only to cultivate students' practical innovation ability, but also to guide them to form a correct outlook on life and values. This requires schools and teachers to focus on cultivating students' ideological and moral quality in teaching, so that they can not only innovate and start businesses in practice, but also establish a correct worldview and outlook on life. At the same time, schools and teachers also need to clarify the relevant capacity cultivation objectives of "three creations" education and professional ideological education, so as to provide effective guidance and support for the overall quality development of students.^[11]

Secondly, the integration of "Three Creations" education and professional ideological education requires the integration of curricula and teaching methods. In tourism management majors, this study suggests that teachers should integrate "three creations" education with professional ideological and political education through a variety of teaching methods and teaching forms. For example, they can guide students to apply their professional knowledge in actual projects by offering innovation and entrepreneurship practice courses, and cultivate their innovation ability and professionalism by combining with the guidance of professional ideological education. In addition, teachers can also make students feel the importance of Civic and Political Education in practice through

case teaching, discussion classes, field research, etc., and improve their "three creations" ability through practical operation.

Once again, the integration of "three creations" education and professional ideological education needs to promote the overall development of students. In tourism management majors, students not only need to master professional knowledge and skills, but also need to have good moral cultivation and social responsibility. Therefore, this study proposes to integrate the guidance of Civic and Political Education into the "Three Creations" education, and to cultivate students' sense of social responsibility and professional personality through life practice and social practice. At the same time, schools and teachers should create a favorable learning environment and social environment, actively guide students to participate in social practice activities, and improve their humanistic literacy and social adaptability.^[12]

Finally, the integration of "Three Creations" education and professional ideological education needs to strengthen the training and support of teachers. Teachers are the key force of collaborative education, and their ability and quality directly affect the implementation effect of collaborative education. Therefore, schools should strengthen the training and support for teachers to improve their professional level and teaching ability. At the same time, schools should also strengthen communication and cooperation among teachers and encourage them to carry out research on curriculum reform and exploration of teaching practice, so as to provide useful experience and lessons for collaborative parenting.

3.2 Ways to enhance the effect of the "Three Creations" education on the cultivation of tourism management majors' civics and politics

First of all, improving the teaching quality of "Three Creations" education is an important way to improve the effect of Civic and Political education. By improving the curriculum and teaching content, teachers can organically combine the "three creations" education with professional ideological education, so that students can cultivate innovative thinking and entrepreneurial awareness while learning professional knowledge. For example, the introduction of innovation and entrepreneurship case study in the curriculum of tourism management, through the analysis of successful tourism enterprises and projects, to stimulate students' innovative potential and entrepreneurial enthusiasm.^[13]

Secondly, providing diversified practice opportunities is one of the important ways to enhance the "Three Creations" education. By organizing students to participate in practical activities such as field trips, practical training and internships, students can be helped to combine theoretical knowledge with practical operation and enhance their practical and innovative abilities. At the same time, practical activities can also cultivate students' sense of teamwork and leadership ability, and provide a more practical and comprehensive experience for their Civic and Political education.

In addition, strengthening students' political education is another important way to enhance the effect of "Three Creations" education. Civic and political education is an important part of cultivating students' correct outlook on life and values, and it is also the key to improving the effect of civic and political education. In the "Three Creations" education of tourism management majors, we should pay attention to guiding students to set up correct life goals and value pursuits, as well as cultivating their sense of social responsibility and civic consciousness. Schools and teachers can strengthen the strength and breadth of civic education by carrying out civic education activities and organizing students to participate in social practice and public welfare activities.^[14]

Finally, the establishment of a good evaluation system is the key to improve the effect of "Three Creations" education. By establishing scientific and effective evaluation standards and methods, we can objectively evaluate the development and growth of students in "Three Creations" education, and provide teachers with references and bases for improvement. At the same time, the evaluation system should focus on the cultivation of comprehensive

quality and innovation ability, not only on the results as the only criterion, which can better stimulate students' learning motivation and enthusiasm.

To sum up, by improving the teaching quality of "Three Creations" education, providing diversified practice opportunities, strengthening students' ideological education, and establishing a good evaluation system, the effect of ideological education in tourism management majors can be effectively improved. These measures will provide useful reference and guidance for the education and teaching reform of tourism management majors, and will also provide broader space and opportunities for students' personal growth and development.

3.3 Continuous Optimization and Reflection of "Three Creations" Education to Enhance the Effect of Civic Parenting in Tourism Management Major

3.3.1 Continuous optimization of collaborative educating strategy

First, strengthen the cultivation of teachers. Teachers specializing in tourism management should have good innovative and entrepreneurial thinking and professionalism, and be able to effectively guide students in innovative and entrepreneurial practices. Therefore, colleges and universities should strengthen the training of teachers, improve their professional ability and teaching level, and cultivate more high-quality teachers with the concepts of "three creations" education and professional ideology.

Secondly, build practice environment. Practice is an important part of "Three Creations" education, and schools should actively create an environment conducive to students' innovation and entrepreneurship practice. We can cooperate with tourism enterprises to establish practice bases, provide more opportunities and platforms for innovation and entrepreneurship, provide students with opportunities for practice and exercise, and cultivate students' innovative consciousness and entrepreneurial ability.

Third, broaden resource channels. Schools should actively cooperate with all sectors of society to broaden resource channels and provide more resource support for students. It can establish partnerships with relevant enterprises to provide students with internship opportunities and employment channels; it can organize industry experts to give lectures and guidance to provide students with innovation and entrepreneurship guidance and assistance.

Fourth, strengthen the construction of evaluation system. Establishing a scientific and reasonable evaluation system can effectively measure students' innovation and entrepreneurship ability and professional ideological and political literacy. The evaluation system should comprehensively consider the students' theoretical learning achievements, practical ability and the effect of Civic and Political

Education, and adopt a variety of evaluation methods and weigh them.^[15]

3.3.2 The reflection of strategy optimization

First, focus on the combination of theory and practice. In the process of collaborative education, tourism management majors should pay attention to the combination of theory and practice. Although the "Three Creations" education emphasizes practice, the theoretical foundation is also very important.

Schools should focus on cultivating students' theoretical thinking ability, and combining theoretical knowledge with practical operation, so that students can use theoretical knowledge to solve practical problems in practice.

Second, focus on personalized development. Schools should fully respect students' individuality and interests, and encourage students to actively carry out innovation and entrepreneurship activities in their professional fields. Flexible elective courses can be set up to meet students' individualized development needs. Teachers and students should establish a good interactive relationship to provide students with personalized guidance and support.

Third, strengthen students' ideological education." One of the synergistic educational goals of "Three Creations" education is to guide students to form a correct outlook on life and values. Professional ideological education is an important way to realize this goal. Schools should strengthen students' ideological and political education,

cultivate students' patriotism, collectivism and social responsibility, and guide students to correctly view the value of entrepreneurship and innovation.

Fourth, constantly improve the innovation and entrepreneurship education model. Innovation is constantly developing and changing, and the innovation and entrepreneurship education model also needs to be constantly improved and perfected. Schools should pay close attention to the dynamics of innovation and entrepreneurship education at home and abroad, and constantly introduce new teaching concepts and methods to promote the innovation of innovation and entrepreneurship education. At the same time, schools should also establish a good feedback mechanism to understand students' feedback on the innovation and entrepreneurship education model and improve the education model in time.

4. Conclusion

In the process of research, this paper found some shortcomings. First, in the evaluation of the implementation of the "three innovations" education, this study has not yet adopted a variety of methods to carry out an objective evaluation. Second, the implementation of collaborative education strategy may face various challenges, such as the lack of teachers' resources and students' awareness and acceptance of ideological education. Future research can further improve the evaluation system to enhance the implementation of the collaborative parenting strategy and explore how to overcome the challenges in order to improve the quality of education and teaching in the tourism management program.

Based on the findings and shortcomings of this study, we propose the following directions and practical suggestions for future research. First, in-depth research can be carried out with more cases to enrich and improve the theoretical framework of the "Three Creations" education and professional civic education model, and empirical research can be carried out to verify its practical effects. Secondly, we can explore how to improve the effect of professional ideology and politics through reforming the cultivation mode and innovating teaching methods. In addition, cooperation with enterprises and social resources can be strengthened to cultivate students' innovative spirit and practical ability, and to prompt students to form a correct outlook on life and values in practical scenarios.

In conclusion, this study proposes an innovative model of collaborative education by exploring the collaborative education of "three creations" education and professional ideology in tourism management majors under the background of new liberal arts. Although some shortcomings were found in the process of the study, the findings of this study provide useful reference and guidance for the education and teaching reform of tourism management majors. Future research can conduct in-depth studies on the assessment system and implementation strategies to further improve the collaborative parenting model, as well as to enhance the educational quality and parenting effect of the tourism management program. At the same time, the research field of collaborative parenting between "Three Creations" education and professional ideology can be further expanded through in-depth case studies and practical exploration.

Acknowledgements

Funded project: Shaanxi Province "14th Five-Year Plan" Education Science Planning 2022 Annual Project "New Liberal Arts Background of Tourism Management Professional "Three Creations"

Education and Professional Civic and Political Concerted Parenting Research" SGH22Y1712 **References**

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